

Career Preference of Senior Secondary School Students in Relation to Peer Group Pressure

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Anu Malhotra
Research Scholar
Department Of Education
Om Sterling Global University
Hisar, Haryana, India,

Jitendera Mishra
Associate Professor
Department Of Education
Om Sterling Global University
Hisar, Haryana, India

Rajender Kumar
Professor and Co-supervisor
Department Of Education
Jan Nayak Ch. Devi Lal College of
Education
Sirsa, Haryana, India

Abstract

In this age of competition and striving for perfection, the students are encountering so many challenges in deciding their career. In the changing world, today everybody let it be the students, teachers and parents, all want to be up to dated. Man has attained refinement through the process of education. Education is a never widening concept. Education is a process of training the individual so as to draw out the best in him and make him able to get success in present competitive age. Peer Group Pressure are very important to help in the field of education and support in career choices. Career preference depends on number of factors like: Peer Group pressure, family climate, intelligence and environment. The present study under consideration was planned to explore the relationship between career preference and Peer Group Pressure of the adolescents. The study found that the coefficient of correlation between career preference and Peer Group Pressure is 0.036 which is lesser than the table value of 0.195 and 0.254 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance respectively. It indicates that the correlation coefficient between career preference and Peer Group Pressure is not significant. Hence, the study reveals no significant correlation exists between career preference and Peer Group Pressure of class 11th school students.

Keywords

Career Preference, Peer Group Pressure, Social freedom, Correlation, Significant Difference, Rural and Urban.

Introduction

In the changing world, today everybody let it be the students, teachers and parents, all want to be updated. Everyone is in need of updated knowledge, approach habits and skills to achieve updated career. The government has planned to give majority to give those subjects and courses which should be based on the students' skills and attitudes. Man directly or indirectly has been trying to educate himself in order to meet the changing demands of life. The system of education has been evolved by the society to train its future citizens who in turn will become the guiding force for developing the society in right direction.

Career is a regular occupation or profession in which one is making a living. Career planning is essential for quality of life and peaceful living. This forms the basis of the person's future life, social recognition and hence contributes towards the development of the country by proper utilization of the human capital (Antoniou, 2010). There was a great reason of unemployment i.e. preferring a wrong career. Career, the base of future plays a very important role in everyone's life. The planning for career is very essential and the students who go to school every day, plan their future according to their dreams.

The Peer Group Pressure may affect the decisive role in deciding the prospective career for a particular student. A regular study can only be maintained by getting the advices of peer group. Efficient learning demands development of good reading and understanding competition in choosing the career. Sometimes Peer Group pressure affect in deciding the career but be careful in selecting the career in field of education and do some extra studies in this context. To study effectively the students are not only necessarily be interested in the subjects of their study, but have to possess the necessary knowledge, skills and proper methods of study. Generally, every student at any educational level possess their talent and interest peculiar to his/her with which he/she goes about their academic tasks. Effective learning not only depends on good teaching but also on following the satisfactory learning procedures. When students use their learning effectively and contextually, learning becomes fruitful. This may further leads to forming good decisions in

selecting their career and it changes the preferences of their future career. Career success of the students can be best attained with gaining proper guidance in choosing right kind of advice from teachers, parents and peer group and attain the requisite learning.

Objective of study

1. To study the career preference of class 11th school students.
2. To study the Peer Group Pressure of class 11th school students.
3. To study the relationship between career preference and Peer Group Pressure of class 11th school students

Review of Literature

Singh and Yadav (2015) study conducted to explore the career choices of 11th class students, the influences their needs had on their career choice had also studied. The data collected from 200 students of Rewari city. Thurston and vocational interest scheduled was used and Tripathi Personal Preference scheduled was used for analysis is of the data. The results of study revealed that the adolescent give highest preference to executive jobs and least to music related jobs. The needs achievement and needs have emerged as top needs and needs difference and need exhibition have got the bottom place. It founded that some needs also influenced the career choices of adolescent.

Nadeem (2016) compared the career preference of male and female in the study of higher secondary students. The study was conducted was conducted by collecting random sample of 200 higher secondary schools Budgam district. The results of the study show that the male and female higher secondary students differ with respect to their career preferences.

Nur Hayati Abd Rahman, Shafinar Ismail, Abdul Rahim Ridzuan, Khairunnisa Abd Samad (2020) from their research on "GRADUATES MINDSET IN DESIGNING THEIR INITIAL CAREER" has aimed to comprehend graduates' perspectives on how they plan their first jobs, whether as job seekers (work in *the* public or private sector) or job creators. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which is causing a rise in graduate unemployment. The variables are Gender, Age, Working Experiences, Field of Study. Data was collected by interviewing the fresh graduates. According to the findings, 80% of the interviewees prefer to be job seekers, while only 20% opt to start their own businesses.

Md. Roknuzzaman Siddiky, Shahana Akter (2021) from their research *On "CAREER CHOICE AND JOB PREPAREDNESS STRATEGIES: A SOCIAL ENVIRONMENTAL PERSPECTIVE"* has investigated the factors determining the students' career choice and find out their job preparedness strategies. Moreover, the study sought to propose a theory which could explain the students' career choice from asocial environmental perspective. Using a structured questionnaire, the researchers themselves conducted telephone interviews with the respondents to gather primary data. Conversely, secondary data were gathered from a variety of pertinent secondary suitable books, journal articles, dissertations, and conference papers are among the sources. According to the study, the majority of respondents' self-study in order to pursue their ideal careers. Despite the fact that career development trainings are crucial for helping students develop their job-related skills, the majority of respondents reported not having received any such trainings.

Kumar Yadav & Kumari, 2023 : High school seniors have dealt with a variety of issues pertaining to the influence of classmates on their academic performance, including issues of social belonging, parental cultural orientation, academic inclination, and academic rigour. Based on the findings, it seems that there are a number of variables related to peer pressure that could influence students' academic achievement. This data demonstrates that students are not adversely affected by peer pressure. Peer pressure in the classroom has a wide-ranging impact on pupils' ability to learn and retain information.

Mathew & Simon, 2024: The results demonstrated that there were significant relationships and differences between academic stress and self-regulation, peer pressure and self-regulation, and academic stress and academic stress among college students. In addition, peer pressure had a substantial influence on academic stress but no apparent effect on self-regulation. These findings emphasise the need of addressing academic stress and peer pressure in order to promote good self-regulation and overall well-being among college students, as well as the complex interactions that affect them.

Main Text

Career Preference

Career selection is one of many important decisions students have to make in determining his future plans for growth and development in his vocational field. Adolescence is a preparatory stage to move towards a career

in the world of work from schools and knowing a career choice at this age is one of the most important of all the developmental processes. Thus, school students in their career decision period needs to explore their thoughts and attitudes about the career in order to choose a suitable career.

The national career development association (NCDA,1984) defines the preferences or planes – a written lists of the short and long terms goals that employee have regarding

their current and future jobs requirements and hence a planned sequence of a formal as well as informal experiences to help in achieving their career goals. According to Okon (2001) intelligence is the important variable that exert a considerable positive influence on career preference. Kochar (2002) is of the view that career preference is that occupation which is having highest positive values among alternative forms of work values. Speete (2002) observe career includes home, community and school and is a continual process that occurs over the period of life-span of the individual.

Peer Group Pressure

Peer pressure is the feeling that someone of your own age is pushing you towards making a certain choice, good or bad. It is a term used to describe how an adolescent behavior is influenced by other adolescents it is the influence that peer group observes or individual exerts that encourages others to change their attitudes, values or behavior to confirm the group norms. It is commonly associated with episodes of adolescence risk taking such as drug abuse, sexual behavior and reckless driving because these activities commonly occur in the company of others. Adolescents are the most socialized into their peer groups and thus are vulnerable so peer pressure. Peers are the primary component of an adolescent's social network and are relied upon more as sources and advice during the development period. (Burmester, 1996). There are many types of peer pressure such as positive peer pressure which is a pressure from others to do right things something that improve your health and social life and make you feel good about your decisions: Negative peer pressure would be when people with hold affection of other usual contact because you have done something offensive particularly to the group's view of right and wrong, heavy peer pressure is the worst peer pressure. It may pressurize the people to smoke, drink or even involve in drugs. Friendly peer pressure refers to the influence from a friend that make someone to do something that he or she may or may not want to do it occurs among people who are familiar to each otherPeer pressure has been called a hallmark of adolescents' experience. Peer conformity in young people is most pronounced with respect to style taste appearance, ideology and values. For a teenager, trying to be fit in and be accepted a big goal and they will often go to extremes to be liked and be popular among their peers.

Ryan (2000) defined peer pressure as when people of your own age encourage or urge you to do something or to keep from doing something else, or mater if you personally want to do it or not.

According to Cambridge Advanced Leamer's Dictionary and Thesaurus (2015)- Peer pressure is the influence that other people of your own age or social class have on the way you behave. Peer pressure means the strong influence of a group especially of children, on members of that group to behave as everyone else does.

So, it can be safely assumed that peer pressure is the influence of a social group on an individual. Peer groups are usually cliques of friends who are about the same age. Peer group play an important role in career decision making in Individual's life. Besides, at the level of decision making among youth, most of the decisions are dependent on ability, education, teacher advice level of counseling with peers and familial background of friends.

By keeping this in view, the investigator felt the need to use a tool which can measure the positive as well as negative effects of pressure from pear on the adolescents as they are also influenced, motivated and inspired by their peers.

Operational definitions

Career Preference - Career means an occupation that a person undertakes for a substantial period of their life. Preference means a greater liking for alternative over another or others. Therefore, career preference refers to those preferences, which are related to a "vocation".

Peer Group Pressure:

Peer pressure is the feeling of pressure by an individual from other age-mates so do something fruitful or harmful) for self and others especially to be accepted or liked by the peer or peer groups. This may result in change of their attitude, values or behavior.

Emergence of The Problem

The review of related literature implies that the importance of career preference has raised several important issues for educational researchers. Researchers have come out with results which are contradicting and complementary to each other. A complete comprehensive picture of career related decisions and the role of negative peer group pressure still seems to be faded. The research therefore, still continues to explore career preference and peer group pressure which may be important factor which influence the career and if we see the present situation where the career preference and peer group pressure of the youths have undergone changes due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Now the learners are independent, getting education on gadgets, there is no direct interaction with the teacher, there is however no burdens of class work and homework and even the routine class tests. So in the present scenario the issues related to the negative peer group pressure of the students and their preference towards career have become important because the students can become lazy as they are not going to school, they

are not following their time-table and because of these circumstances they may lose their interest in their specific career choices. Therefore the investigator sought to see the relationship between career preference and peer group pressure of the adolescents in the present context.

Statement of the Problem

Career Preference of Senior Secondary School Students in Relation to Peer Group pressure.

Tools Used

Career Preference Record (CPR-BB) -By Dr. Vivek Bhargava and Dr. Rajshree Bhargava (2023)- National Psychological Corporation, Agra

Analysis

The data analyzed for present study through the administration various test in order to study the career preference as a correlate of Per Group Pressure of students. For this purpose score of career preference record developed by Bhargawa and Bhargava (2023) were obtained from the resources. And the score of Peer Group Pressure were developed. After this various statistical computations have been carried out by applying descriptive statistics. The descriptive statistics such as mean, median, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis etc used in the present study.

Table1: Mean, Median, S.D., Skewness and Kurtosis of Career Preference

N	Mean	Median	Satandard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
100	17.26	18.01	7.50	-0.16	-0.53

Table1 shows mean median, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis of career preference of students. This is supported by the fact that the values of mean and median are 17.26 and 18.01 respectively which are closed to each other. The value of standard deviation is 7.50. The value of skewness is -0.16 which shows that mean scores are negatively skewed or skewed left, meaning that the left tail is longer. The value of kurtosis - 0.53, which is less than 0.263 and shows that the distribution of scores in this case is leptokurtic, which do not pile up on any side of the polygon thus proving its normal distribution.

Table2: Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis of Peer Group Pressure

N	Mean	Median	Satandard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
100	122.6	135.5	71.82	0.37	-0.96

Table 2 shows that the values of mean, median are 122.6 and 135.5 respectively closed to each other. The value of standard deviation is 71.82 and skewness is 0.37 wherein the value of kurtosis is -0.96 which is less than 0.263, which shows frequency distribution is leptokurtic.

The Hypothesis" there exist no significant relation between Career Preference and Peer Group Preference" is tested by employing Pearson's coefficient of correlation. For which the raw scores obtained by students were taken by the investigator and the relationship between the variables was calculated. The results are depicted in Table 3.

Table3: Correlation between Career Preference and Peer Group Pressure

Variables	N	Co-efficeint of Co-relation (r)
Career Preference and Peer Group Pressure	100	*0.058

Degree of freedom = 98; *Table value at 0.05 level=0.195 and value at 0.01 level =0.254

Table 3 reveals that the coefficient of correlation between career preference and Peer Group Pressure is 0.058, which is lesser than the table value of 0.195 and 0.254 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance respectively. Therefore, the coefficient of correlation between career preference and Peer Group Pressure is not significant. Hence the hypothesis i.e. there is no significant correlation between career preference and Peer Group Pressure is retained.

Sample of the Study

The data was collected through the technique of multistage randomization of clusters. At the first stage schools were randomly selected from the various schools. At the second stage sections were selected randomly from the schools thus chosen. At the third stage students were selected randomly from the sections chosen. A total of 100 students were selected for the present study.

Fig 1 Sample of the Study

Delimitation of the Study

The study was delimited to 100 students of class 11 of Sirsa District only with respect to the variables of career preference and Peer Group Pressure.

Peer Pressure Scale (PPS-KA) - By Ms. Amandeep Kaur (2023)- National Psychological Corporation, Agra.

Procedure of the Study

To carry out the study descriptive survey method was used. The descriptive survey research is not only about gathering and tabulation of data, but it also intends to interpret the meaning and significance of research problem. Besides, this description, it often makes comparison and contrast of the existing evidences to arrive at suitable conclusion.

Conclusion

The result of the present study supports the hypothesis that there is no significant correlation between career preference and Peer Group Pressure of class 11th school students. It varies from person to person at individual level. It depends upon situation and environment of individual to choosing their career. The results of the study reveal that:

The mean and median scores of Career preference of 100 students is 17.26 and 18.01 respectively which are closer to each other.

The mean and the median scores of Peer Group Pressure is 122.6 and 135.5 and coefficient of correlation is 0.058 which is not significant and clearly shows that there exist no relationship between career preference and Peer Group Pressure.

Educational Implications

1. The study can be of some help to parents to make their children more aware about their career choices and goals.
2. The study can help in planning better guidance programs to the students for their career preference.
3. The study can help to understand the level of Peer Group Pressure among students.
4. The study can aware in adoption of Peer Group Pressure and strategies and negative and positive peer group pressure towards career preference.

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